

Letter To The Editor

Mirtazapine Induced Edema

Yavuz YÜCEL, Ertuğrul UZAR

Dicle University Faculty of Medicine, Department of Neurology, DİYARBAKIR

ÖZET

Mirtazapine bağlı ödem

Mirtazapin nadir olarak ödem gibi ciddi yan etkilere neden olabilir. Migren ve depresyon tedavisi için mirtazapin alan ve pretibial ödem gelişen bir olguyu sunduk. Mirtazapin tedavisinin kesilmesi ile 2 gün içinde pretibial ödem kayboldu. Sonuçta klinisyenlerin mirtazapine bağlı doz ile ilişkili ve geriye dönebilen ödemin farkında olmaları gereklidir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Mirtazapin; yan etki; ödem

ABSTRACT

Mirtazapine may rarely cause serious adverse effects such as edema. Herein, we describe a patient receiving mirtazapine for depression and migraine who developed pretibial edema during treatment. Pretibial edema disappeared within two days after the cessation of the therapy. In conclusion, physicians need to be aware of the potential risk of the dose related reversible edema due to mirtazapine.

Key Words: Mirtazapine; adverse effect; edema

Mirtazapine is a widely used noradrenergic and specific serotonergic antidepressant¹. Mirtazapine may rarely cause serious adverse effects such as facial edema, allergy and bone marrow toxicity².

Herein, we describe a patient receiving mirtazapine for depression and migraine who developed pretibial edema during treatment with mirtazapine.

30-year-old woman was presented with increased migraine attack, depressive symptoms and insomnia. The patient was receiving escitalopram 10 mg/day for the last three years for treatment of depression. Mirtazapine 30 mg/day was added to therapy for migraine prophylaxis and insomnia. Three days after starting mirtazapine, patients reported significant bilateral pretibial edema and facial edema. Physical examination was unremarkable except for +2 pitting pretibial and facial edema. She had no past history of vascular, hepatic, cardiac, immunologic or renal failures. Her renal, liver, thyroid function tests and urinalysis results, serum sodium, chloride, protein and albumin levels were all within the normal range. The chest radiography, echocardiography, abdominal ultrasonography, venous doppler results have revealed no abnormal results. We considered that the edema due to mirtazapine caused the idiosyncratic reaction and mirtazapine treatment was discontinued. Within two days discontinuing mirtazapine, pretibial edema disappeared.

As far as we know, peripheral edema due to antidepressant drugs is seen extremely rare^{3,4}. In the literature, we found only one case reporting peripheral edema secondary to mirtazapine⁶. Barnett et al. reported ten cases of peripheral edema associated with trazodone⁴. In the present case, we present a patient receiving mirtazapine for depression and migraine who developed pretibial edema during treatment with mirtazapine. Given that there are many probable causes of edema, we excluded all the other possible causes of edema with extensive clinical, radiological, laboratory work-up. The edema occurred after starting mirtazapine, hence we thought that edema was due to mirtazapine. To the best of our knowledge, this case is the second report in the literature. The pathophysiological mechanism of mirtazapine induced edema is not clear. Possibly, mirtazapine may cause edema as an idiosyncratic reaction. Escitalopram and mirtazapine are negligible inhibitors of CYP isoenzymes in vitro. The interaction between these two drugs is less likely than other second-generation antidepressants to interact with co-administered medications⁵.

In conclusion, clinicians should be aware of this uncommon but significant side effect of mirtazapine. However, further clinical investigations are needed to confirm our findings and to elucidate the mechanism.

REFERENCES

1. Stimmel GL, Dopheide JA, Stahl SM. Mirtazapine: an antidepressant with noradrenergic and specific serotonergic effects. *Pharmacotherapy* 1997;17(1):10-21.
2. Biswas PN, Wilton LV, Shakir SAW. The pharmacovigilance of mirtazapine: results of a prescription event monitoring study on 13 554 patients in England. *J Psychopharmacol* 2003;17(1):121-6.
3. Kutscher EC, Lund BC, Hartman BA. Peripheral edema associated with mirtazapine. *Ann Pharmacother* 2001;35(11):1494-5.
4. Barnett J, Frances A, Kocsis J, Brown R, Mann JJ. Peripheral edema associated with trazodone: a report of ten cases. *J Clin Psychopharmacol* 1985;5(3):161-4.

5. Spina E, Santoro V, D'Arrigo C. Clinically relevant pharmacokinetic drug interactions with second-generation antidepressants: an update. *Clin Ther* 2008;30(7):1206-27.

Correspondence:

Yavuz YÜCEL M.D.
Dicle Üniversitesi Faculty of Medicine Department of Neurology, Diyarbakir
e-mail: yucelyavuz@mynet.com
Yazının geldiği tarih : 10.10.2008
Yayına kabul tarihi : 17.03.2011